

Policy Brief

Are We Getting Ready for An Africa Custom Union? “It Depends on Overcoming the Implementation Challenges of the AfCFTA”.

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Executive Summary

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) is a flagship project of the Agenda 2063 of the African Union and a quantum leap towards a single African market as enshrined in the Africa Economic Treaty. While the realization of the AfCFTA is a significant step in the regions integration agenda, the phase two of this agenda, a comprehensive Customs Union, is yet to take-off. This policy brief assesses whether Africa is institutionally, legally, and operationally poised for this second phase of the continent’s economic integration. Though there has been pocket of progress, challenges persist for the full implementation of the AfCFTA five years after its take-off, which include disparities in readiness, customs systems integration, and overlapping regional arrangements which is slowing down progress. This briefing identifies and discusses the challenges besetting the implementation of the AfCFTA, it discusses the readiness for an Africa customs union (ACU) and proposes strategic actions for AU organs, RECs, national governments, and to accelerate and harmonize progress.

Background / Context

Formally, the AfCFTA journey began some decades ago with the signing of the Abuja Treaty in 1991 - a standalone agreement that articulates a clear plan to establish an AEC. The Treaty formalized the AEC which laid the foundation for the regional economic integration in Africa. As of 2023, the Abuja Treaty has been fully subscribed to by the AU 54 Member States having appended their signature to it, while 50 had ratified. One of the objectives of the Treaty was to establish a Free Trade Area, and to do this, the Regional Economic Communities and the geopolitical zones of the continent where to serve as a foundation stone.

There are six stages that the AEC was to follow sequentially for the next four decades after the Treaty came into force. These stages are in consonance with the Balassa approach for deepening economic integration starting with free trade agreement to economic union. Although the Abuja Treaty makes no mention of a continental FTA, it recognizes that a continental customs union (CU) cannot bypass the FTA stage in any of the RECs. The Treaty consolidates the FTA at the REC level. The AfCFTA was therefore established in line with the vision of the Abuja Treaty, using the most practical alternative route that considered that a continental FTA was a necessary precursor for a continental customs union. Given the fact that RECs are the building blocks for the

continental integration, the AU has successfully supported the consolidation of existing RECs; and built new RECs in regions where none existed. It is working to stabilize and eliminate tariff and NTBs within RECs, coordinate and harmonize activities as well as supported the establishment of FTAs and Customs Union in the different RECs. The RECs FTAs and Customs Union lead to the regional AfCFTA and is expected to snowball to the Africa Customs Union.

This brief discusses key findings on AfCFTA Implementation since the signing of the Agreement half a decade ago. Importantly, it identifies customs union related features and map it to the challenges deviling the full implementation of the AfCFTA implementation, and concludes on the possible policy recommendations.

Key Findings on AfCFTA implementation

Ratification and Domestication Gaps

As of 2025, several countries have not domesticated AfCFTA rules into national law. The AfCFTA stands as a transformative project for Africa’s economic integration, with 48 of 55 African Union member states having ratified the agreement as of early 2025. Eritrea remains the only AU member yet to sign the agreement. Ratification signals a country’s formal consent to be bound by the AfCFTA, but it is only one step in a multi-stage process required for the agreement to become effective at the national level. While ratification is widespread, domestication—the process of enacting AfCFTA rules into domestic law—lags in several countries. In dualist legal systems, such as Nigeria’s, international treaties like the AfCFTA do not automatically have the force of law domestically. Instead, they require explicit legislative action to be integrated into national law. For instance, Nigeria’s constitution mandates that treaties must be enacted by the National Assembly to be enforceable; without domestication, citizens and businesses cannot rely on AfCFTA provisions in national courts. Consequently, the domestication gap in several countries creates practical barriers. Countries that have not domesticated AfCFTA rules cannot fully operationalize the agreement, creating uncertainties for businesses if faced with legal issues, as AfCFTA provisions cannot be invoked or enforced domestically. At the end, the pace of intra-African trade liberalization slows, undermining the continent’s integration goals.

Table 1: Number of Africa Countries that have followed the Stages of the AfCFTA Legal Lifecycle

Legal Stage	Lifecycle	Description	Number of Countries	Notes / Examples
Signing		Expresses political intent; not legally binding	54 out of 55	54 AU member states have signed the AfCFTA Agreement; Eritrea has not signed
Ratification		Confirms legal commitment via legislative approval	47-46 countries	47 countries had ratified by August 2024; Liberia ratified in July 2024 making 47; Mozambique expected soon
Gazetting		Official publication in national gazette, marking activation	Not precisely reported	Gazetting is country-specific; some countries like Nigeria have

			gazetted the Agreement after ratification
Domestication	Integration of AfCFTA provisions into national law	At least non confirmed	Countries are at various stages but comprehensive data is limited

Source: Author's description.

As of 2025, while the majority of African states have ratified the AfCFTA, several have yet to complete domestication, stalling the full realization of the agreement's benefits. Bridging this gap requires targeted legislative action, capacity building, and coordination among governments, regional bodies, and the private sector to ensure AfCFTA rules are embedded in national legal frameworks and become a practical reality for African businesses and citizens.

Disjointed Customs Systems

National customs procedures are fragmented, with different levels of digitalization and interoperability. National customs systems across Africa remain fragmented, characterized by varying levels of digitalization and limited interoperability, which hampers efficient trade facilitation and regional integration. Many countries still rely *on siloed customs platforms* that are not fully connected internally or with other national agencies such as tax authorities, port systems, and quarantine services. This fragmentation leads to inefficiencies, increased risk of errors, and opportunities for data manipulation.

Efforts to digitalize customs processes have seen progress in some countries, with web-based customs clearance systems gradually replacing manual, paper-based procedures. However, the pace and extent of these upgrades differ widely across the continent. For example, Nigeria has achieved about 90% digital integration in customs operations through initiatives like the B'Odogwu platform, advanced scanners, and officer training, yet it continues to advocate for broader improvements in digital infrastructure and interconnectivity across West and Central Africa. At the same time, interoperability challenges are compounded by the use of different customs management systems within regional blocs. In the Southern African Customs Union (SACU), member states employ diverse platforms such as ASYCUDA World, iCBS, and Crimson Logic, which complicates seamless data exchange. Pilot projects have shown that real-time data exchange is technically feasible but remain hindered by legislative, data protection, and coordination issues.

On the positive side, some African ports and countries have demonstrated the benefits of integrating customs with port management and national single windows. Benin's interoperability efforts have led to a revenue increase of over 30%, while Côte d'Ivoire and Guinea have improved logistics and reduced processing times through digital platforms. At the continental level, the African Union is advancing interoperability frameworks for digital identity and data exchange, recognizing that trust, standardization, and secure data sharing are critical to transforming fragmented customs and trade systems into a cohesive digital ecosystem. The vision encompasses cross-border data flows that respect privacy and sovereignty, enabling smoother trade and integration under the AfCFTA.

Services Liberalization Lag

Trade in services is yet to pick up despite the establishment of the services protocols. Trade in services under the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) has yet to gain significant momentum despite the establishment of the Protocol on Trade in Services, which entered into force in 2019. The Protocol aims to progressively liberalize services trade across member states, focusing on priority sectors such as business, communication, financial, tourism, and transport services. However, actual liberalization and implementation have been slow, with many countries still finalizing sector-specific commitments and aligning national laws to enable effective administration of the new rules.

Several factors contribute to this lag. Unlike trade in goods, services trade liberalization does not involve tariffs but rather requires the removal or simplification of regulatory barriers, which are often complex and vary widely across countries. The Protocol incorporates special provisions for Least Developed Countries, allowing transitional periods and technical assistance, but the practical application of these measures remains unclear. Additionally, the diversity in economic development levels and regulatory environments among member states has led to staggered implementation and cautious commitments.

The slow uptake undermines the potential benefits of the AfCFTA in boosting intra-African trade, industrial development, and economic growth. The service sector is a critical enabler of Africa's growth, representing a significant share of GDP and employment, yet its productivity lags behind other regions. Accelerating the liberalization of services trade is essential to unlock new market opportunities, enhance competitiveness, and foster innovation across the continent.

Limited Private Sector Engagement

Businesses often lack awareness or capacity to leverage AfCFTA. Limited private sector engagement in the AfCFTA is a significant challenge, largely due to businesses' lack of awareness and capacity to fully leverage the agreement's opportunities. Despite the private sector accounting for over 80% of Africa's production and providing about 90% of employment, many enterprises, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), remain insufficiently informed or prepared to engage with AfCFTA mechanisms effectively¹. SMEs, which constitute over 90% of African businesses and employ a large share of women and youth, face barriers such as limited access to

¹ The problem is that several Africa Government are yet to sufficiently fund advocacies and capacity building for AfCFTA in their respective countries. Funding mainly comes from development partners. Key funders include AfDB, EU, World Bank, UNECA, ITC, GIZ, the former USAID, and private sector foundations.

finance, inadequate infrastructure, and regulatory complexities that hinder their participation in intra-African trade.

The African Union and AfCFTA Secretariat recognize the private sector as a critical driver of economic growth and have initiated public-private partnerships and strategic programs to enhance engagement. However, gaps persist in translating these efforts into widespread private sector ownership and utilization of AfCFTA benefits. Many businesses lack the capacity to navigate the complex regulatory environment and to exploit new market opportunities created by the AfCFTA, resulting in underutilization of the agreement's potential to boost intra-African trade by over 50% and increase GDP significantly.

Moreover, political and institutional challenges, such as mismatches between continental aspirations and national priorities, limited trade facilitation infrastructure, and varying institutional capacities, further constrain private sector involvement. While policies exist, there is a pressing need for tailored policies that address the unique needs of SMEs and for enhanced efforts to raise awareness and build capacity among businesses to foster inclusive participation. Strengthening partnerships with business associations and improving dissemination of AfCFTA implementation strategies are crucial steps to create an enabling ecosystem that empowers African businesses to benefit fully from the continental market.

Overlapping REC Commitments

Dual memberships lead to incoherent tariff applications. Overlapping memberships in Regional Economic Communities (RECs) pose a significant challenge to the coherent application of tariffs under the AfCFTA. Many African countries belong simultaneously to multiple RECs, each with its own trade rules, tariff schedules, and rules of origin (RoO). This multiplicity creates a "spaghetti bowl" effect (Figure 1), where conflicting and duplicative regulations increase complexity and transaction costs for traders and customs officials. For example, countries that are members of both COMESA and SADC face difficulties in determining which RoO to apply, leading to delays and inefficiencies in customs procedures. The coexistence of multiple trade regimes results in inconsistent tariff applications and undermines the AfCFTA's goal of simplifying and harmonizing trade across the continent.

Figure 1: Regional Trade Arrangement in Africa as the 2019, Source: MacLeod, Luke and Guepie (2023, p.41)

The AfCFTA Agreement acknowledges these challenges and includes provisions, such as Article 19, aimed at managing the interface between the AfCFTA and existing RECs to promote harmonization and reduce regulatory costs. However, *weak enforcement mechanisms, institutional capacity gaps, and differing interpretations of principles like subsidiarity and complementarity among stakeholders hinder progress*. The preservation of RECs' *acquis communautaire*, while politically important, complicates efforts to streamline trade rules continent-wide. Furthermore, overlapping memberships can dilute member states' commitment to integration and increase administrative burdens, particularly affecting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that lack resources to navigate complex regulatory environments. Without effective coordination and harmonization of tariffs, RoO, and customs procedures, the full potential of the AfCFTA to boost intra-African trade and economic integration remains constrained.

Slow Tariff Phase-Down

Sensitive and excluded products have delayed full liberalization. The slow tariff phase-down under the AfCFTA is primarily due to the classification of certain products as sensitive or excluded, which delays full liberalization. Member states have agreed to liberalize tariffs on 90% of goods within five years for non-Least Developed Countries (non-LDCs) and ten years for Least Developed Countries (LDCs). However, 7% of tariff lines are designated as sensitive products, requiring longer phase-down periods—up to 10 years for non-LDCs and 13 years for LDCs—and 3% of tariff lines are completely excluded from liberalization to protect sectors critical for food security, national security, fiscal revenue, and industrial development.

Six countries—Ethiopia, Madagascar, Malawi, Sudan, Zambia, and Zimbabwe—have secured an extended 15-year phase-down period due to specific development challenges they face. This extended timeline reflects the need for special and differential treatment to accommodate varying levels of economic development across the continent. The phased approach aims to balance trade liberalization with protecting vulnerable industries and ensuring socio-economic stability. However, the phased tariff reduction has contributed to delays in the full operationalization of the AfCFTA, as negotiations on rules of origin and sector-specific commitments continue, particularly for complex sectors like textiles and motor vehicles. These sectors account for about 10% of the rules of origin and have more restrictive product-specific rules, complicating tariff liberalization efforts. Furthermore, infrastructural challenges have slowed implementation.

Despite these delays, the AfCFTA Secretariat has developed complementary strategies, including the Guided Trade Initiative which has been abolished just recently and trade facilitation tools, to accelerate liberalization and support intra-African trade growth. The ultimate goal remains the elimination of tariffs on 97% of goods over a phased timeline, fostering economic integration and industrialization across Africa.

Is Africa Getting Ready for an Africa Customs Union?

The race to building a single Africa customs Union (ACU) have begun (Table2). Several RECs such as **ECOWAS, SACU, and EAC** have already established functioning customs unions with common external tariffs and harmonized customs procedures. Others like **COMESA, SADC, and ECCAS** are at various stages of progressing toward customs union status. These RECs serve as the **building blocks** for the broader African Customs Union envisioned under the Africa Economic Community framework. Their experiences in implementing common external tariffs, coordinating customs procedures, and facilitating intra-regional trade provide valuable lessons and foundations for continent-wide integration. However, as note earlier, overlapping memberships and inconsistent policy implementation across these RECs pose challenges to harmonization, which must be addressed to achieve a seamless ACU.

... Overlapping memberships and inconsistent policy implementation across RECs pose challenges to harmonization, which must be addressed to achieve a seamless Single African Custom Union

Table 2: Custom Union Status of Regional Economic Communities (REC) in Africa

<i>Regional Economic Community (REC)</i>	<i>Customs Union Status</i>	<i>Member Countries / Region</i>	<i>Key Features and Role</i>
<i>Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)</i>	Established Customs Union	West Africa (12 countries). Three countries have left ECOWAS – Niger, Burkina Faso and Mali	Implements a Common External Tariff (CET), free movement of goods and people, and the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS). Serves as a leading example of customs union integration.
<i>Southern African Customs Union (SACU)</i>	Oldest Customs Union (since 1910)	Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, South Africa, Eswatini	Maintains a CET, shares customs revenues, and coordinates trade policies. Provides a model for revenue sharing and policy coordination.

<i>East African Community (EAC)</i>	Customs Union in operation	Burundi, Kenya, Rwanda, South Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda	Operates a CET and Customs Union Protocol; aims for deeper integration including a Monetary Union and Political Federation.
<i>Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA)</i>	Customs Union (partial implementation)	21 countries across Eastern and Southern Africa	Has a CET, but implementation varies; part of the Tripartite Free Trade Area (TFTA) with EAC and SADC to harmonize trade.
<i>Southern African Development Community (SADC)</i>	Working toward Customs Union	16 countries in Southern Africa	Proposed accelerated timeline for a customs union; overlaps with SACU and COMESA memberships complicate integration.
<i>Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS)</i>	Working toward Free Trade Area and Customs Union	Central Africa (11 countries)	Focuses on gradual creation of a customs union and free trade area within 20 years of inception; faces challenges due to instability.
<i>Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD)</i>	Not yet a customs union	Horn of Africa and parts of East Africa (8 countries)	Primarily focused on peace and security; trade integration efforts ongoing but customs union not yet established.
<i>Arab Maghreb Union (AMU)</i>	Customs Union agreed but largely inactive	North Africa (5 countries: Algeria, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Tunisia)	Customs union protocols exist but political and economic differences have stalled progress.

Following these challenges besetting the AfCFTA, it is necessary to ask: Is the continent still ready to implement its customs union? To answer this question, there is a need to identify customs union related features and map it to the challenges deviling the full implementation of the AfCFTA implementation. The challenges currently facing the AfCFTA—such as ratification and domestication gaps, disjointed customs systems, services liberalization lag, limited private sector engagement, overlapping REC commitments, and slow tariff phase-down—directly undermine the core features essential for a functioning customs union.

<i>AfCFTA Challenges</i>	<i>Related Customs Union Feature</i>	<i>Impact on Customs Union Actualization</i>
<i>Ratification and Domestication Gaps</i>	Elimination of Internal Tariffs	Without uniform domestication, internal tariffs and non-tariff barriers persist, preventing free movement of goods and services. A customs union fundamentally requires the elimination of internal trade barriers among member states, enabling goods and services to move freely without tariffs or quotas. However, the domestication gaps mean that AfCFTA rules are not uniformly enforceable at the national level, preventing the consistent removal of internal tariffs and non-tariff barriers that a customs union demands.

*Disjointed
Customs Systems*

Harmonized
Customs
Procedures

Fragmented and non-interoperable customs systems increase costs and delays, undermining seamless trade facilitation. disjointed customs systems with varying degrees of digitalization and interoperability obstruct the harmonization and simplification of customs procedures—a key feature of customs unions that reduces administrative costs and facilitates seamless intra-union trade. Without integrated and efficient customs operations, the “pay once, move freely” principle that defines customs unions cannot be realize.

*Services
Liberalization
Lag*

Inclusion of
Services Trade

Slow services liberalization limits economic integration beyond goods, reducing the union’s scope and competitiveness. The services liberalization lag also weakens the customs union’s scope. While customs unions primarily focus on goods, modern economic integration increasingly includes services as a vital component. The slow uptake of services liberalization limits the union’s ability to foster deeper economic cooperation and innovation, which are among the benefits of customs unions through enhanced competition and market expansion.

*Limited Private
Sector
Engagement*

Market
Expansion and
Increased
Competition

Low awareness and capacity among businesses hinder utilization of the integrated market, limiting trade growth and innovation. Limited private sector engagement further hampers the customs union’s effectiveness. Customs unions thrive on active participation from businesses that can leverage the larger integrated market. Without sufficient awareness and capacity-building, especially among SMEs, the potential for increased trade flows and economic integration remains unrealized.

*Overlapping
REC
Commitments*

Common
External Tariff
(CET)

Conflicting tariff schedules and rules create incoherence, preventing the establishment of a uniform external tariff. Moreover, overlapping REC commitments create incoherent tariff applications and regulatory conflicts, directly contradicting the customs union’s requirement for a common external tariff (CET) and uniform trade policies. Dual memberships lead to tariff inconsistencies and trade deflection, issues that customs unions are designed to resolve by enforcing a single external tariff and harmonized rules.

*Slow Tariff
Phase-Down*

Gradual Tariff
Removal and
Market
Integration

Extended protection of sensitive products delays full liberalization, fragmenting the market and weakening integration. The slow tariff phase-down, especially on sensitive and excluded products, delays the full liberalization of intra-union trade. Customs unions depend on the gradual but decisive removal of tariffs

within the union and the establishment of a CET externally. Prolonged transition periods and exclusions fragment the market, weakening the union's integrative power.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations to prepare the Continent for a Single Africa Customs Union

This policy brief has considered whether the continent is ready to implement the customs union as enshrined in the Treaty Establishing the Africa Economic Community in the 1960s. The brief look at the current implementation progress, by considering the impediment to the full implementation of the AfCFTA, since this first phase to the regional continental integration is a prerequisite require for the full implementation of regional single Africa custom union. The challenges militating against the full implementation of the AfCFTA has been noted to include: domestication gaps, disjointed customs systems, services liberalization lag, limited private sector engagement, overlapping REC commitments, and slow tariff phase-down. While the AfCFTA is Africa's most ambitious integration initiative, readiness for a full Customs Union is uneven – as not all REC has transformed into a Custom Union. Stronger coordination, harmonization of policies, and capacity-building are essential. Without these, the Customs Union dream envision by the continents forefathers may remain a theoretical objective rather than a functional reality. To realize these dreams, the following recommendations are important, albeit some recommendations are ready been implementation but it necessary reiterate them again.

Recommendation for the AU and AfCFTA Secretariat

- ***Set clear benchmarks for Customs Union formation:*** Develop a phased timeline with measurable milestones aligned to the Abuja Treaty and AfCFTA objectives (e.g., tariff harmonization targets, elimination of non-tariff barriers). In addition, use data-driven assessments of member states' readiness (customs capacity, infrastructure, legal frameworks). Publish progress reports and scorecards to promote transparency and accountability among member states if such reports are unavailable. At the same time facilitate technical working groups with RECs and member states to agree on common benchmarks and timelines. And finally leverage lessons from existing customs unions (e.g., EAC, SADC) to define realistic benchmarks.
- ***Establish a Pan-African Customs IT Harmonization roadmap:*** Conduct a continent-wide audit of existing customs IT systems across member states and RECs. It is important to develop standards for interoperability, data exchange, and security aligned with international best practices (e.g., WCO Data Model). Furthermore, design a phased implementation plan for a unified customs IT platform supporting electronic Single Window systems and real-time data sharing. It is necessary to secure funding and technical

partnerships for capacity building and infrastructure upgrades. Encourage Member States to promote adoption of common digital customs documentation (e.g., AfCFTA Certificate of Origin). It is also necessary to coordinate with RECs to ensure regional IT systems align with the continental roadmap.

- ***Coordinate with RECs to align trade protocols:*** Establish formal coordination mechanisms (e.g., joint committees, liaison offices) between AfCFTA Secretariat and REC secretariats. Also continue to strengthen the harmonization rules of origin, customs procedures, and trade facilitation measures to reduce duplication and overlap. At the same time facilitate regular information sharing and joint capacity-building workshops. Encourage RECs to adapt their policies and protocols (such as investment, trade and industrial protocols) to be consistent with AfCFTA agreements, respecting the principle of preserving the acquis.

Recommendation For AU Member States

- ***Expedite legal domestication and implement national AfCFTA strategies.*** Review and amend national trade, customs, and investment laws to align with AfCFTA protocols. In addition, establish or strengthen national AfCFTA committees or focal points within relevant ministries. It is important that Member States implement developed national implementation strategies and roadmaps with timelines and responsible agencies (*no more lip service*). Conduct stakeholder consultations (private sector, civil society) to ensure buy-in and smooth implementation. Allocate budgetary and human resources to support domestication and implementation efforts.
- ***Upgrade customs infrastructure and border logistics:*** Member States should invest in modern customs facilities, including scanners, electronic data interchange, and automated clearance systems. Invest and improve on transport and logistics infrastructure at border posts (roads, warehousing, inspection facilities) considering the multimodal transport system. At the same time, Member States should implement risk management and trade facilitation measures to speed up clearance times. Continue to train customs officials on AfCFTA rules, digital tools, and trade facilitation best practices at least once annually and collaborate with Africa Member states especially border countries in establishing efficient joint border posts and harmonized procedures.
- ***Establish dedicated AfCFTA implementation task forces:*** If not on ground, create multi-sectoral teams with representatives from trade, customs, finance, transport, and private sector. Define clear mandates, targets, and reporting lines for the task forces. Ensure regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting on implementation progress. Facilitate coordination between national, regional, and continental levels. Use task forces to identify bottlenecks and propose corrective actions promptly.

Recommendation for RECs:

- ***Harmonize rules of origin and trade documentation with AfCFTA:*** Review existing REC rules of origin and align them with the AfCFTA Rules of Origin Manual to ensure uniform interpretation and application. Standardize trade documents such as certificates of origin, customs declarations, and transit documents. Facilitate joint training for customs officers and traders on harmonized rules and documentation. Establish mechanisms to resolve disputes related to rules of origin within the REC framework.

- **Facilitate cross-border trade facilitation mechanisms:** Implement and promote regional Single Window systems for customs clearance. Coordinate border management reforms including joint inspections and risk management. Harmonize sanitary and phytosanitary standards and technical regulations to ease movement of goods. Develop regional transport corridors and logistics hubs to reduce transit times and costs. Promote information sharing platforms to alert traders on border procedures and requirements.

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